

Systematic review

1. * Review title.

Inhaled nitric oxide for hospitalised COVID-19-patients: a systematic review

3. * Anticipated or actual start date.

26 October 2020

4. * Anticipated completion date.

01 February 2021

5. * Stage of review at time of this submission.

The review has not yet started: Yes

Review stage	Started	Completed
Preliminary searches	Yes	Yes
Piloting of the study selection process	Yes	No
Formal screening of search results against eligibility criteria	No	No
Data extraction	No	No
Risk of bias (quality) assessment	No	No
Data analysis	No	No

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PLEASE NOTE this information will be published in the PROSPERO record so please do not enter private information

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10. * Organisational affiliation of the review.

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12. * Funding sources/sponsors.

This review is funded solely by departmental resources.

13. * Conflicts of interest.

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

14. Collaborators.

N/A

15. * Review question.

Is inhaled nitric oxide effective and safe for the treatment of hospitalised COVID-19-patients compared to standard care?

16. * Searches.

We will search the following databases and sources for published, unpublished and ongoing studies, from 1 January 2020 to 26 October 2020.

- MEDLINE via PubMed
- Cochrane COVID-19 Study Register (<https://covid-19.cochrane.org/>) including MEDLINE (PubMed), Embase, ClinicalTrials.gov, WHO ICTRP, and medRxiv
- Living Overview of the Evidence (L·OVE) platform (<https://app.iloveevidence.com/loves/>)

We will search the Retraction Watch Database for retracted studies (<https://retractionwatch.com/retracted-coronavirus-covid-19-papers/>).

We will search the reference lists of included studies, relevant systematic reviews, and current COVID-19 treatment guidelines for eligible studies.

We will not restrict the search to any language.

All references obtained by the search will be imported into Rayyan OCRI (<https://rayyan.qcri.org/>).

17. URL to search strategy.

MEDLINE (PubMed)

#1 (coronavirus OR "corona virus" OR coronavirinae OR coronaviridae OR betacoronavirus OR covid19 OR "covid 19" OR nCoV OR "CoV 2" OR CoV2 OR sarscov2 OR 2019nCoV OR "novel CoV" OR "wuhan virus") OR ((wuhan OR hubei OR huanan) AND ("severe acute respiratory" OR pneumonia) AND (outbreak)) OR "Coronavirus"[Mesh] OR "Coronavirus Infections"[Mesh] OR "COVID-19" [Supplementary Concept] OR "severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2" [Supplementary Concept] OR "Betacoronavirus"[Mesh]

#2 „Nitric Oxide“ [MeSH Terms] OR (Nitrogen Monoxide*) OR (Oxide, Nitric*) OR (mononitrogen monoxide*) OR (Monoxide, Nitrogen*) OR (Monoxide, Mononitrogen*) OR (NO*) OR (nitric oxide*) OR (iNO*) OR (nitric-oxide*) OR (nitrogen-monoxide*) OR (mononitrogen-monoxide*)

#3 #1 AND #2

18. * Condition or domain being studied.

COVID-19. Respiratory tract infection caused by the new coronavirus SARS-CoV-2.

19. * Participants/population.

Inclusion criteria: Patients of any age or sex with confirmed COVID-19 respiratory tract infection that were admitted to the hospital, i.e. patients' state has to comply with a score of minimum 4 on the WHO Clinical Progression Scale.

No restrictions will be applied regarding the extent of ventilatory support. Awake and spontaneously breathing patients are included as well as those receiving any form of non-invasive or invasive mechanical ventilation.

Exclusion criteria: Confirmed COVID-19 diagnosis that does not require hospital admission and respiratory tract infections caused by any other viruses than SARS-CoV-2.

20. * Intervention(s), exposure(s).

Any inhalational regimen of nitric oxide (NO) administration.

NO is mostly applied as inhalational gas, but especially with the emergence of COVID-19 new approaches have been introduced, e.g. gargle solution or nasal spray. These application forms aim to reduce primarily the local viral load. Non-inhalational administration routes of nitric oxide will not be eligible.

21. * Comparator(s)/control.

Standard of care or placebo.

Studies using additional treatments (e.g. antiviral therapy) will only be included if those treatments do not differ between intervention (NO) and control group.

22. * Types of study to be included.

We will include randomised controlled studies (RCTs) and non-standard RCT designs (cluster-randomised and cross-over trials).

In case of insufficient evidence from RCTs, we will include pro- and retrospective controlled non-randomised studies of interventions (NRSIs), including quasi-randomised controlled trials, controlled before-after studies, and interrupted time series (with comparison group).

In case of insufficient evidence from RCTs and controlled NRSIs, we will include non-controlled NRSIs, such as case reports and case series. Results will be descriptively summarised and reported in tables only.

23. Context.

On 11 March 2020, the WHO has announced COVID-19 outbreak to be a global pandemic and so far (October 2020), over 1 million deaths were caused by SARS-CoV-2. In addition to the research for targeted antiviral therapies, there is urgent

need for supplementary measures in order to improve the outcome of hospitalised COVID-19 patients. Nitric oxide (NO) - normally administered to patients as inhalational gas - is a signalling molecule that causes vasodilatation resulting in improved lung perfusion and oxygenation (Griffiths et al.). In this function, it has been used in critically ill ARDS patients since the late 1990s. Especially in times of limited intensive care resources, it is important to find evidence if hospitalised COVID-19 patients with respiratory tract infections could potentially benefit from this treatment at any stage of their disease. Since hypercoagulation seems to be responsible for severe complications in COVID-19 patients, NO is of particular interest for its additional anti-inflammatory and antithrombotic effects (Wang et al.).

Aim of this systematic review is to summarize and assess the current evidence of effectiveness and safety of inhalational nitric oxide for hospitalised COVID-19 patients.

Griffiths, M. J. and T. W. Evans (2005). "Inhaled nitric oxide therapy in adults." N Engl J Med 353(25): 2683-2695.

Wang, T., et al. (2003). "Inhaled nitric oxide in 2003: a review of its mechanisms of action." Can J Anaesth 50(8): 839-846.

24. * Main outcome(s).

- All-cause mortality (day 7, 14, 28, 60, 90)
- Mortality (time to event)
- Improvement of clinical symptoms, assessed by need for respiratory support with standardised scales (e.g. WHO Clinical Progression Scale) at up to 7 days, up to 14 days, and up to 30 days

*** Measures of effect**

For continuous outcomes using the same scale we will perform analyses using the mean difference (MD) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs). For continuous outcomes measured with different scales, we will perform analyses using the standardised mean difference (SMD).

We will extract and report hazard ratios (HRs) for time-to-event outcomes.

For dichotomous outcomes, we will perform the analyses using the pooled risk ratio (RR) with a 95% CI.

25. * Additional outcome(s).

- Time to discharge from hospital
- Admission to the intensive care unit (ICU)
- Length of stay in ICU
- Duration of mechanical ventilation
- Frequency of Intubation
- Intubation (time to event)
- Weaning failure, need for tracheotomy, frequency of extracorporeal life support (ECLS)

- MODS score
- Virological response (RT-PCR)
- Need for vasopressors
- Frequency of thromboembolic events

*** Measures of effect**

For continuous outcomes using the same scale we will perform analyses using the MD with 95% confidence intervals (CIs). For continuous outcomes measured with different scales, we will perform analyses using the SMD.

We will extract and report hazard ratios (HRs) for time-to-event outcomes. For dichotomous outcomes, we will perform the analyses using the pooled RR with a 95% CI.

26. * Data extraction (selection and coding).

Two review authors will independently identify studies that might be included in this review. If encountering disagreements, we will consult a third review author and resolve all discrepancies by discussion. We will record the selection process in sufficient detail, complete a PRISMA flow diagram and list all studies excluded during full-text screening along with reasons for exclusion.

Two review authors will independently extract data using a standardised data extraction form, including details of the study, participants, intervention, comparator, and outcomes (developed by the review authors). If necessary, we will try to receive missing data by contacting the authors of relevant articles. At each step of data extraction, we will resolve discrepancies by discussion within the group of review authors.

27. * Risk of bias (quality) assessment.

Randomised controlled trials

Two review authors will independently assess the risk of bias for RCTs using the Cochrane 'Risk of bias' tool 2 (RoB 2). The review authors will resolve disagreements by discussion with a third review author. The effect of interest is the effect of assignment at baseline, regardless of whether the interventions are received as intended (the 'intention-to-treat effect'). Risk of bias will be assessed for all results reported in the included studies, which are specified as one of the outcomes of the current review, and contributing to the review's 'Summary of findings' table.

Five domains will be assessed by answering signalling questions and will be judged as "low risk of bias", "some concerns" or "high risk of bias".

1. Bias arising from the randomization process
2. Bias due to deviations from intended interventions
3. Bias due to missing outcome data
4. Bias in measurement of the outcome
5. Bias in selection of the reported result

We will use the RoB 2 Excel tool to implement RoB 2. The full RoB 2 data (e.g. completed Excel tool) will be stored in an online repository (e.g. Zenodo).

We will summarize the overall risk of bias for each result (outcome). Briefly, we will judge the result to be at "overall low risk of bias" if all domains will be assessed as "low risk of bias". The result is judged to be at "some overall concerns" if at least one domain for this result will be assessed as "some concerns", but not to be at high risk of bias for any domain. The result is judged to be at "overall high risk of bias" if at least one domain for this result will be assessed as "high risk of bias".

Controlled non-randomised studies of interventions

Two review authors will independently assess eligible NRSIs for methodological quality and risk of bias (using the Risk Of Bias in Non-randomised Studies - of Interventions (ROBINS-I) tool). The review authors will resolve any disagreements regarding quality assessments by discussion with a third author.

The categories for 'Risk of bias' judgements for controlled NRSIs using ROBINS-I are "low risk", "moderate risk", "serious risk" and "critical risk" of bias.

We will assess the following domains of bias.

1. Bias due to confounding
2. Bias in selection of participants into the study
3. Bias in classification of interventions
4. Bias due to deviations from intended interventions
5. Bias due to missing data
6. Bias in measurement of outcomes
7. Bias in selection of the reported result

For every criterion, a judgement using one of five response options will be possible.

- Yes
- Probably yes

- Probably no
- No
- No information

Non-controlled, non-randomised studies of interventions

We will not assess the risk of bias of non-controlled, non-randomised studies of interventions.

28. * Strategy for data synthesis.

We will not combine data from different study designs. We will perform separate meta-analyses for RCTs and controlled NRSIs. In case of insufficient evidence from RCTs and controlled NRSIs, we will include non-controlled NRSIs, such as case reports and case series. Results of non-controlled NRSIs will be descriptively summarised and reported in tables only.

If the clinical and methodological characteristics of individual studies were sufficiently homogeneous, we will pool the data in a meta-analysis. We will use the random-effects model as we assume that the intervention effects will be related but will not be the same for the included studies.

For dichotomous outcomes, we will use the Mantel-Haenszel method. For continuous outcomes or time-to-event outcomes, we will use the inverse variance method. We will use RevMan 5.4 for analysis.

We will measure statistical heterogeneity using the Chi² test, the I² statistic, and the 95% prediction interval (PI) for random-effects meta-analysis. We will restrict the calculation of a 95% PI to meta-analyses with ≥ 4 studies (≥ 200 participants), since the interval would be imprecise when a summary estimate was based on only a few small studies. We will use the R package meta to calculate 95% PIs. We will declare statistical heterogeneity if $P < 0.1$ for the Chi² statistic, or $I^2 \geq 40\%$ (40% to 60%: may represent moderate heterogeneity; 50% to 90%: may represent substantial heterogeneity; 75% to 100%: considerable heterogeneity), or the range of the 95% PI revealed a different clinical interpretation of the effect estimate compared to the 95% CI.

GRADE and Summary of Findings tables

We will use the GRADE approach to assess the certainty of evidence for all registered outcomes. We will present the results of the GRADE assessment in Summary of Findings tables.

29. * Analysis of subgroups or subsets.

We will investigate statistical heterogeneity by subgroup analysis, if more than 10 studies will be available. We will perform subgroup analyses to calculate RR, MD, or SMD in conjunction with the corresponding CI for each subgroup if statistical

heterogeneity is present ($P < 0.01$ for the Chi^2 test of heterogeneity or a different clinical conclusion of 95% CI versus 95% PI).

We will perform subgroup analyses for the following characteristics:

- Severity of condition (moderate vs. severe disease as defined by the WHO clinical progression scale)
- Interventional NO regimen (dose of NO, duration of administration)

30. * Type and method of review.

Type of review: systematic review

Health area of the review: Respiratory disorders; Infections and infestations;

31. Language.

English

32. * Country.

Germany

36. Keywords.

systematic review; nitric oxide; COVID-19; coronavirus disease 2019; severe acute respiratory syndrome *coronavirus 2*

38. * Current review status.

Review ongoing